

LIST OF TALKS

Authors	Title	Session	Date / Time
Allee et al.,	Two Shelf Edge Marine Protected Areas in the Eastern Gulf of Mexico	6	Tue, 17h40
Anderson et al.,	Mapping and Predicting Benthic Habitats, Biological Assemblages, and Biodiversity across the Carnarvon Shelf, Western Australia	1	Tue, 13h50
Armstrong et al.,	Mesophotic Coral Ecosystems of Puerto Rico	5	Thu, 13h50
Barrell et al. <i>Student Award</i>	Geostatistical and landscape analysis of fine-scale eelgrass (<i>Zostera marina</i>) habitat patterns	3	Wed, 16h20
Barrie et al.,	Inland Tidal Seas of the Northeastern Pacific	6	Tue, 17h40
Bax et al.,	Identifying ecologically and biologically significant deepwater habitat	4	Thu, 10h50
Bergersen et al.,	Application of an Integrated GIS and 4D Visualisation Tool Kit to the NIWA Cook Strait Data Set	1	Tue, 16h20
Black et al.,	A GIS analysis of New Zealand's Trawl Footprint	1	Tue, 14h50
Bourillet et al.,	Geomorphological characterisation of cold water corals habitats (Bay of Biscay, NE Atlantic)	3	Wed, 14h30
Bowden et al.,	Multibeam sonar in the deep-sea: can it really tell us much about benthic habitats and fauna?	1	Tue, 14h10
Brooke et al.,	Seabed diversity of the shelf surrounding Lord Howe Island	6	Tue, 17h40
Bürk et al.,	Seafloor sediment classification in a tidal inlet channel: The influence of shell debris and seafloor rugosity	1	Tue, 10h50
Canals et al.,	The Catalan submarine canyon heads, NW Mediterranean Sea: coupling seafloor morphology and biological diversity	3	Wed, 14h50
Clark et al., <i>Keynote speaker</i>	Habitat as a proxy for biodiversity: how can seamount classification systems aid the scientific design of marine protected areas	4	Thu, 8h30
Cogswell et al.,	Using GIS Models to Delimit Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (VME) Boundaries in the Northwest Atlantic Regulatory Area (NRA)	4	Thu, 11h10
Collin et al.,	Spatial predictability of species diversity and abundance of epimacrobenthos in turbid nearshore using bathymetric LiDAR	2	Wed, 9h40
Colquhoun et al.,	Habitat-based assessment of epibenthos using AUV Optical imagery, northwest Australia	1	Tue, 14h30
D'angelo et al.,	Phanerogame meadows: a characteristic habitat of the Mediterranean shelf. Examples from the Tyrrhenian Sea	5	Thu, 14h50
De Mol et al.,	Predictive cold-water coral habitat mapping in the Western Mediterranean Sea	4	Thu, 11h30
De Mol et al.,	Alboran Seamounts, Western Mediterranean sea	6	Tue, 17h40
Diesing et al.,	Rocky reef in the central English Channel	6	Tue, 17h40
Dolan et al.,	Mapping and modelling seabed nature-types in Norway's MAREANO programme – lessons learned	5	Thu, 16h20
Downie et al.,	The Influence of Physical Parameters on Benthic Communities – A Case Study in the Gulf of Finland, the Baltic Sea	3	Thu, 9h20
Dunstan et al.,	Predicting Groups of Species: application of finite mixture models to species prediction	2	Wed, 13h30
Friedman et al., <i>Student Award</i>	Towards Automated Classification of Benthic Environments using Rugosity, Slope and Aspect from Bathymetric Stereo Image Reconstructions	2	Wed, 10h50
Gauthier et al.,	Quantifying trawling impacts on deep-sea ecosystems using ROV video and scanning-sonar data	3	Wed, 10h00
Gonzalez-Mirelis et al., <i>Student Award</i>	Deriving "mappable" biological assemblages from underwater footage using classification tree models	2	Wed, 11h30
Greene et al.,	Deep-Water Forage Habitats - The Next Step Forward in Marine Benthic Habitat Mapping?	1	Tue, 11h30
Greene et al.,	Outer Shelf Rocky Habitats of Alaska	6	Tue, 17h40
Heap et al.,	Seabed mapping for Australia's energy security	5	Thu, 14h10
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Kingon <i>Student Award</i>	A system for mapping nearshore, marine habitats on a tight budget	1	Tue, 10h00
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Lawton et al.,	Relationships between seabed assemblages in the Gulf of Maine and their physical environment using Random Forests	3	Wed, 16h00
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